

Question raised by requestor

Are there guidelines to kill properly a llama or an alpaca in a slaughterhouse? One of our slaughterhouses received one alpaca for slaughter and they are asking for good practices (handling, restraint, and killing). The question was received on 22 August, 2024.

Answer

Introduction

Llamas (*Lama glama*), guanacos (*L. guanicoe*), vicuñas (*Vicugna vicugna*), and alpacas (*V. pacos*) are known collectively as lamoids and belong to the South American camelids (also referred to as the New World camelids) (1). Alpacas and llamas are becoming more popular in Europe (2) and especially alpaca farming, albeit of limited financial importance, has been growing steadily since the 1990s (3–4). For instance, Germany has well-established farms of both llamas and alpacas (5). They are mostly kept for grazing, fleece production, as hobby animals or as tourist attractions. Even though they are not primarily kept for their meat, occasionally they need to be slaughtered or killed.

Lamoids are gregarious, grazing animals. They are able to interbreed and produce fertile offspring. Lamoids must be shorn periodically (every 1 to 2 years) to prevent them from becoming over-fleeced and as a result exposed to possible health risks (e.g., heat stress and skin infections) (1, 6). The lamoids' evolutionary development occurred in a relatively cool climate, rendering them sensitive to excessive heat and humidity. Being obligate nasal breathers (7), lamoids dissipate heat through sweating via the relatively fibreless area on the ventral abdomen, axillary space, and inside of the thighs (8). Factors that may contribute to the production of excess body heat include e.g., racing, fighting, transportation and prolonged restraint.

Legislation

The Council regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 of 24 September 2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing lays down rules for the killing of animals bred or kept for the production of food, wool, skin, fur or other products as well as the killing of animals for the purpose of depopulation and for related operations. According to the definition of 'animal' (Article 2) the regulation applies to '*any vertebrate animal excluding reptiles and amphibians*', which means that the regulation must be applied when slaughtering lamoids or killing them for the purpose of depopulation. Article 3 states that '*animals shall be spared any avoidable pain, distress or suffering during their killing and related operations*'.

Anyone who handles or is responsible for live animals in a slaughterhouse must have a certificate of competence (Articles 7 and 21 of Regulation (EC) 1099/2009). This certificate of competence lists the operations (e.g., handling, stunning, bleeding), the type of stunning equipment covered and the categories of animals to which the certificate of competence applies. Thus, when slaughtering lamoids, this category must be mentioned in the certificate of competence.

The Council regulation (EC) No 1/2005 of 22 December 2004 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations applies to the transport of live vertebrate animals carried out within the EU, including the specific checks to be carried out by officials on consignments entering or leaving the customs territory of the EU. Article 2 states that '*no person shall transport animals or cause animals to be transported in a way likely to cause injury or undue suffering to them*'. Annex I, Chapter 1 states that '*no animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey, and all animals shall be transported in conditions guaranteed not to cause them injury or unnecessary suffering*'.

Note that for different Member States there may be national legislation stricter than the EU legislation.

Handling

Competent handling of lamoids is essential to their husbandry. Like other animals, lamoids shall be treated and transported in a way that minimises the risk of pain, stress and injury. Adult males and females should travel separately. Lamoids have a strong herd instinct and attempting to separate animals from the herd can induce significant stress in the individual. Visual access will decrease stress if physical contact is not possible (9). Some lamoids are used to being haltered, but the rostral portion of the muzzle has minimal cartilage and can be unintentionally collapsed when restrained using halters or some mechanical restraints, resulting in suffocation (10–12). Approaching the animal from

the front will trigger its flight response. Handlers should move animals quietly, walking slowly behind them, without using driving devices that cause unnecessary pain and/or distress (10). Animals should not be forced to move faster than normal walking speed. Lamoids usually lay down in sternal recumbency during transport, so cushioning should be provided in the form of rubber matting, carpet or straw, especially on long journeys (12).

Restraint

Isolating and restraining a lamoid will induce stress in the animal with the result of it becoming restless and moving its head. Nevertheless, sufficient restraint is necessary for an accurate placement of the stunning equipment. The World Organisation for Animal Health's (WOAH, formerly OIE) Terrestrial code indicates the following acceptable restraint methods for lamoids during slaughter: stunning pen/box, halter (for halter-trained animals) and lateral restraint using cradle/crush (13). Inappropriate and excessive restraint has been associated with signs of distress (15).

Stunning

According to the Council regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 Annex I, the following methods can be used for stunning of all species: penetrative captive bolt device and firearm with free projectile. For situations other than slaughter, a lethal injection can be used. Stunning of domestic lamoids is normally performed with a penetrating captive bolt device. Studies on different species have suggested that it is the kinetic energy transmitted to the skull by the bolt that induces unconsciousness (contrecoup injury) while the physical damage by the bolt to specific brain structures is responsible for producing irrecoverable unconsciousness (16). A recent study suggests that for alpacas, captive bolt injury induces unconsciousness principally by direct physical trauma (from the bolt to the structures of the brain and brainstem), while the contrecoup injury seems less important (14).

In a British study, alpacas were stunned using either a frontal or a crown position (14). The frontal position was defined as the intersection of two lines crossing from each eye to the opposite ear, with the shot aiming towards the brainstem. Crown shots were defined as a shot placed on the highest point of the head, while aiming down to the base of the jaw. The crown shot is also used for stunning hornless sheep. Almost all alpacas were shot using the crown position due to the difficulty of placing the captive bolt device in the front without eliciting the flight response of the animal. A different study proved that the crown position for stunning was effective for inducing unconsciousness in alpacas (17). The British study concluded that ideally, the handler should be positioned slightly behind the alpaca's shoulder, bringing the captive bolt device forwards to the shooting position from the back of the head (14).

Immediately after shooting, the animals must be assessed for clinical signs of consciousness. According to EFSA, signs of inefficient stunning (not species-specific) are: rhythmic breathing, constricted pupils, attempts to raise the head, vocalisation during stunning, presence of corneal reflexes, rotation of the eyeballs, response to painful stimuli and presence of ear muscle tone (18). Animals that display signs of incomplete stunning must immediately be re-stunned.

Studies suggest that for alpacas eyeball rotation is not a reliable indicator for the assessment of success or failure of captive bolt stunning for inducing insensibility (14). In sheep for instance, severe hind-leg convulsive kicking is often observed following captive bolt stunning and is associated with the onset of insensibility. In alpacas, however, convulsive kicking is often absent or mild. Therefore, it is considered an unreliable indicator for the assessment of stunning quality in these animals. Studies on cattle have revealed that more than one sign should be considered when assessing stunning efficiency as it will increase the likelihood of differentiating between efficient and inefficient stunning (19). Stunning efficiency is essential for animal welfare, but it also influences the meat quality (20). Stress reduces the glycogen content of muscle fibres; an essential component of the meat maturation process (21).

In conclusion, captive bolt stunning seems to be a reliable method for inducing unconsciousness and insensibility in lamoids and the top of the head (crown position) aiming down to the base of the jaw, maximises damage to the brain and brainstem.

Bleeding

Even if captive bolt stunning induces unconsciousness and insensibility, it does not immediately kill the animal. Therefore, the animal has to be bled, even when the meat is not intended for consumption. After stunning, the animal must be checked for the absence of consciousness and total insensibility before bleeding is initiated. It is of utmost

importance that the animal remains unconscious until death occurs. Signs of death (not species-specific) include no sign of heartbeat after bleeding has stopped, no breathing, enlarged pupils with no response to light, all muscles are relaxed and no movements of the legs (22). The absence of signs of life should be verified before carcass processing begins. Studies indicate that an incision close to the jawline (severing the carotid arteries and jugular veins) or a chest stick or thoracic stab in the thoracic cavity (severing the aorta) result in efficient bleeding for lamoids (14). A ventral neck incision in the lower regions of the neck can be difficult since the lateral processes of the cervical vertebrae create a U-shaped tunnel (figure 1). This anatomical structure is thought to protect the animals during fighting.

Figure 1: Site of venepuncture in llamas (dotted line). Due to the anatomical structure of the cervical vertebrae of lamoids, a jawline incision at the venepuncture site is preferred to a lower neck incision. ©Sheri Amsel 2024. Used by permission.

Summary

Lamoids are gregarious animals. Isolating and restraining a lamoid will induce stress in the animal, with the result of it becoming restless and moving its head. Nevertheless, sufficient restraint is necessary for an accurate placement of the stunning equipment. Ideally, the handler should stand behind the shoulder of the animal bringing the captive bolt device forward to the head without entering the animal's field of vision. The captive bolt device should be placed at the top of the head (crown position) aiming down to the base of the jaw to maximise damage to the brain and brainstem. After stunning, the animal must be checked for absence of consciousness and complete insensibility before bleeding is initiated. In case of signs of ineffective stunning or if in doubt, the animal must immediately be re-stunned. It is of utmost importance that the animal remains unconscious until death occurs (e.g., the heart stops) and that no signs of life are visible before carcass processing begins.

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